

Electrochemical Studies on Lead Electrode

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An electrochemical study on the behaviour of freshly electroplated and aged lead electrodes in solutions of varying pH , initially free from lead ions, has been made; the probable existence of an oxide film on the surface of metals has also been discussed.

Behaviour of these electrodes has been examined in universal buffer mixtures at different temperatures. By comparing the results obtained, the behaviour in alkaline range is found to be governed by PbO , but in the acid range it is governed by a persistent phosphate film in phosphate buffers or an oxide in acetate buffers.

Although the lead electrode (Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Longmans, Green and Co., London, Vol. 7, 1947, p. 649; Nayer and Pande. *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, **27A**, 343; Compton and Mendizza, *Corrosion*, 1949, **5**, 194; Rell, *ibid.*, p. 261; ElWakkeed and Salem, Electrochem. Soc. Meeting, Cincinnati, Ohio, 1955, No. 60; Ito and Shibane, *Chem. Abs.*, 1957, **51**, 6308) has been extensively investigated, no systematic study of its behaviour in solutions of varying pH is available. The present investigation throws light on its behaviour in solutions of different pH in presence of air.

EXPERIMENTAL

The electroplated lead electrode used was prepared after Mathio (*Zhur. Priklad Khim.*, 1956, **28**, 236) from 0.8-1.0*N* solutions of lead plumbite using a current of 10 *m.a.*/cm² of a platinum plate electrode for 30 minutes. The anode was a rod of pure lead provided by Sherring Kahlbaum Company.

Buffer solutions of varying pH (2.98 to 10.97) were prepared according to Smith ("Analytical Processes. A Physico-Chemical Interpretation", 1949, p.442). Another series of buffer solutions covering the pH range 1.7 to 11.88 was also prepared (Britton, "Hydrogen Ions", Vol. I, 1955, p. 365, Chapman and Hall). For the extreme acid and alkaline ranges, nitric acid and sodium hydroxide solutions were used. The pH values of these solutions were checked with the hydrogen electrode and, when possible, with the quinhydrone electrode. All buffer solutions were used undiluted.

The behaviour of the lead electrode as an indicator electrode was examined in the titration of the universal buffer mixtures with 0.2*M*- $NaOH$ solutions at different temperatures, ranging from 25° to 50°. For this purpose a water thermostat was used where temperature was kept constant within a range of $\pm 0.05^\circ$.

Electrical Measurements.—The measurements were carried out in duplicate with different stock solutions. The potential of the lead electrode was measured by coupling it with a saturated calomel electrode as half cell, of which the potential value amounted to 0.245 volt at 25°. Measurements were made with a Cambridge potentiometer.

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows that with the electroplated lead electrode, slopes obtained from pH 1.0 to 8.0 deviate from the theoretical for the hydrogen electrode. The potentials from pH 8.0 to 12.6 are linear function of the pH of the solution. At the extreme alkaline ranges, the electrode shows an irregular variation in potential. The E°_H value for the range (8 to 12.6) was found to be + 0.250 volt.

FIG. 1. Electroplated lead electrode in acetate buffer solution of varying pH in air.

Fig. 2 (A and B) shows the potential—pH curves obtained in phosphate buffer solutions after 4 and 24 hours. The potential values obtained in acid regions A_1 and B_1 deviate from the hydrogen electrode, $\Delta E/\Delta pH$ is 32mv. In curves A_2 and B_2 the potential is linear giving the E°_H values as + 0.188v and + 0.248v respectively. The potential value obtained at pH 11.3 and 11.8 are much lower than expected values.

In aqueous solutions, oxide film formation in air is usually attributed to the transfer

of electrons to dissolved oxygen, transforming it into OH^- ions which are attracted to the metal lattice, forming an oxide film (ElWakked and Salem, *loc. cit.*).

FIG. 2.(A) Equilibrium values of lead electrode
in universal phosphate buffer after 4 hrs.
(B) The same after 24 hrs.

To ascertain which type of oxide is formed on the electrodeposited lead electrode in air, one can calculate the free energy change (Latimer, "Oxidation Potentials", Prentice Hall, 1953, pp.39, 152) of the reaction:

to be +11440 cal. This gives E°_{H} value of 0.248 volt. This indicates that PbO is the oxide responsible for the linearity of the potential— pH curves in Figs. 1 and 2.

In the alkali range pH 12.6 to 13.8 (Fig. 1) and pH 11 to 12 (Fig. 2), the lead oxide formed, owing to its great solubility in such solutions, will lead to variation in the pH ; the activity of the Pb^{2+} in the solution at the interphase causing it to decrease, the potential value measured deviates from that expected. The local change of pH in the vicinity of the electrode was found previously for mercury, tungsten, and tin (ElWakked *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, **56**, 621; 1955, **59**, 1004; *J. Chem.Soc.*, 1957, 3770).

In the acid range of pH 1 to 6 (Fig. 2, A, and B,) it is suggested that in this region a persisting film of lead secondary phosphate is formed on the surface of the electrodes. The results can be expressed by the equation:

$$E = E'_0 - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln [\text{HPO}_4^{2-}]$$

It can be shown theoretically that up to pH 6, the activity of secondary phosphate ion is inversely proportional to H^+ ion activity. That is

$$\begin{aligned} E &= E''_0 + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln [\text{H}^+] \\ &= E''_0 - 0.029 \text{ pH at } 25^\circ. \end{aligned}$$

This is in good agreement with the results obtained for the electrode $\text{Pb}/\text{PbHPO}_4^{2-}$.

Lead electrode was next used as an indicator electrode in titration of a universal buffer

FIG. 3. (A) Fresh lead electrode in universal buffer titration.
(B) Aged lead electrode in " " "

mixture against $0.2M$ - NaOH solution. A freshly electroplated and an aged lead electrodes were used; the latter was aged by leaving it in solution of pH 9 for 3 days to ensure complete formation of an oxide layer. Fig 3B shows the potential values for the aged electrode which vary linearly with the pH . The value for E''_0 for this electrode was found to be $+0.252$ volt, indicating that the potential is governed by PbO . The fresh electrode in the universal buffer mixture titration (Fig. 3A) exhibits a slope of 32 mv per unit pH , showing that the potential within the pH range 1 to 6 is governed by the primary formation of a phosphate layer. Above pH 8.5, the deviation from linearity is attributed to the slow replacement of PbO .

Titration curves for the fresh electrode at temperatures higher than 35° are similar to those obtained after 24 hours in the phosphate buffers (Fig. 2, B, and B₂) at 25° .